

Paper 5

FIPPS & INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE ROOT AND FOUNDATION**P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal², A. Bhuimali³, Kalishankar Tiwary⁴, R. Rajesh⁵**¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India³Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India⁴Dean (Science & Management), Raiganj University, West Bengal, India⁵Principal, Rohini College of Engineering and Technology, TN, India**Corresponding Author:** pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Within Information Science there are various concepts and among these Information Privacy and Security is important one. Within this security among the important topics the Fair Information Practice is important one. Fair Information Practice in short is called as FIPPs. It is the result of commission's enquiry into the web in which online entities collect various personal information and also assure that practice in information is fair enough. The Fair Information Practice is a core for healthy information privacy protection. It is important to note that FTC has been engaged regarding the online privacy from 1995. The Fair Information Practice basically was proposed in the year 1973 in the report called US Secretaries Advisory Committee on Automated Personal Data System. It was proposed to talk about records, computers and Rights of the Citizen. The fundamental contribution of this committee was to design and development of codes for fair information practice for the betterment of Automated Personal Data System. It is important to note that this commission might also have played a big role in development of Fair Information Practice Principle (FIIPs) in 1977 as mentioned in their report called Personal Privacy in an Information Society. The Information assurance is about the design, development, management of information related policies. It talks about the assurance of the content and information having manual and technological attributes. Information Assurance is the broader area of Security related areas. The FIIP is an important affair of Information Assurance. As Information Assurance is about the policy and framework designing hence in this paper several affairs leading to FIPPs, its role and importance, its characteristics, features and functions have been described in brief manner.

Keywords: Information Assurance, Fair Information Practice Principle, FIPPs, Information Security, IT Laws, Information Policies

1. Introduction

Information Assurance is a topic of the Information Science and Technology. This is the latest addition in Security and Privacy segment. Information Assurance deals with the both manual and computational security related affairs leading to database, websites and networks etc. Information Assurance is broad domain which is also closely associated with different

legal and managerial affairs leading to security policies; which include design, development, management etc. Cyber law, IT Act, Policies on information, Data and Information Privacy etc including their protections are also under the jurisdiction of Information Assurance [1], [5]. This field is concerned about the technologies as well [2], [3], [7]. Many of the academicians, organizations and institutions are using Information Assurance as synonym with other field viz. IT Security, Information Security and Cyber Security; however there are differences. Information Assurance deals with manual information privacy/ security related affairs and also legal affairs such as designing and formulation of security related concerns viz. Information Policy, Information Privacy, Information Security etc [6], [18]. Information Assurance and its development normally depend on various kind of objective, methods and procedure and among these Fair Information Practice Principles are important. FIPPs are core for suitable and sophisticated information development.

2. Objective and Agenda

This paper is conceptual as well as theoretical in nature and deals with various aims and objectives and among these, few important are included—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance in brief with reference to the characteristics and features.
- To know about the core functions and objectives of Information Assurance with reference to the current trends.
- To dig out the latest on Information Assurance with special focus on information protection policies.
- To learn about the Fair Information Practice Principles including its meaning, characteristics and features.
- To know about the steps and process of good information practice and with reference to the Fair Information Practice Principles.

3. Information Assurance: Overview

Information assurance (IA) is the safeguard mechanism for the security, privacy and integrity of data which are used by the individuals as well as organizations. Here it deals with the occupations related with the managing the risks and also its uses [4], [9]. The IA also deals with the processing, storing, as well as transferring of data. As a complex task, Information assurance applies in different places regarding data management in both digital and physical means. It is worthy to note that, Information assurance is concerned about the affairs in electronic device privacy and security [8], [18], [21]. The reputed and renowned organization viz. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) explain that *any measures that protect and defend information and information systems by ensuring their availability, integrity, authentication, confidentiality, and non-repudiation. These measures include providing for restoration of information systems by incorporating protection, detection, and reaction capabilities*—As Information assurance.

Fig: 1-The smaller and brooders knowledge and practice field of Security related areas

4. Information Assurance: Characteristics with Function

Information Assurance is a broad area for information privacy management and technological solutions; and there are many features and functions in this field viz.

- Information Assurance may be considered for the manual as well as technological areas. In manual areas it is the aspects related to design, development of information privacy policies and framework etc [10], [20], [27].
- Information assurance is for making information available to every entities to the concerned one and in a right place.
- The data privacy, Information Privacy, protection become easy with the Information Assurance from different unauthorized and illegal access of information.
- Technological security is the core of Information Assurance and these are lies on information security and also IT security.
- Information Assurance promotes and helps in reading homeland security viz. terrorism, cyber terrorism, cyber war.
- To ensure and managing mobile security, network privacy, security and assurance, database etc Information Assurance is highly recommended.
- Designs, development, security of database and information system become easy with Information Assurance practice.
- Various areas viz. cloud security, infrastructure management, and trust management are the core of Information Assurance.

- Strategies on information management, risk management of information including technological means are the important factor for better Information Assurance practice.

5. Information Protection Policy

Information protection employs security solutions, encryption, and other technologies, as well as policies and processes, to secure information. Information protection can be thought of as a sub-discipline or component of information assurance. While both share a goal of maintaining the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of information, information protection is specifically focused on achieving this through information security, whereas information assurance focuses on ensuring the quality, reliability, and retrievability of information in addition to keeping it protected [11], [18], [23].

FIPPs?

Information Assurance is a broad field within Information Science and within this field there are various concepts. Among these, Fair Information Practice is important one which is called as FIPPs. The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) is a core for healthy information privacy protection designing, development and management. The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) has been engaged as an online privacy from 1995. The commission of The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) here consider following principle as a core:

- Notice or awareness
- Choice or consent
- Problem with choice or consent
- Access or participation
- Integrity or security

In the year 1973, The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) was proposed in the report (*named as US Secretaries Advisory Committee on Automated Personal Data System*). The affairs leading to record, computers and Right of the Citizen basically covered under the Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) [12], [22], [28]. The concerned committee developed the Fair Information Practice Principles (FIPPs) due to design and development of codes for healthy information practice for Automated Personal Data System. It is worthy that; this commission played a big role in development of Fair Information Practice Principle in their report called Personal Privacy in an Information Society [14], [18], [26].

It is a fact that different countries have initiated privacy law. So, FIIPs also developed rapidly with a focus on International implications of privacy regulation. The Council of Europe in the year 1980 has adopted convention for the protection of individuals with regard to automated processing of personal data.

At the same time, OECD guidelines have been proposed by the organization for economic co-operation and development (OECD). Hence, it is important to note that Council of Europe Convention, OECD guidelines, European Union Data Protection Directives play a vital role for the formation of FIPPs principles. Moreover, these organizations have revised and extended the original US statement of FIPPs [14], [19], [25].

FIPPs & Core Principles

A Healthy Fair Information Practice Principles basically depends on various types of process and methods. The core principles of Fair Information Practice Principles include the following (also refer fig:2 for more clarification)—

1. **Notice:** It is important to note that every consumer should get information on different kind of information regarding best information practice. Ultimately regarding notice or awareness following should be taken into consideration:
 - Identification of the entity collecting the data.
 - A suitable place for the user and uses to which data will be used or put.
 - The nature of the data collected and the way of collection.
 - Steps taken for ensuring confidentiality, integrity and quality of data [16], [19], [24].
2. **Choice or content:** Choice or content is an important part of fair information practice. It is actually the giving consumer option regarding the content. More importantly choice is related with the secondary use of information apart from urgent requirement information collector. The following two are typical model for choice viz.-

i) **OPT-ON**

ii) **OPT-OUT**

In first method consumer basically give permission for their information to be used for other purposes. Without this permission this information handling are not possible. Whereas the second option OPT-OUT requires users to decline permission for other uses. Basically both of the system is designed for better information transparency.

Fig: 2 The core principle of Fair Information Practice Principles

3. **Access or participation:** It is an important part within fair information practice principle. Here all the data and information should be collected and verified with proper accuracy. It is worthy to note that access of information should be inexpensive and timely otherwise it is very difficult to use information for the consumer [17], [20].
4. **Integrity and security:** Within fair information practice principle integrity talks about this security of the information. Here all the information should be secured, if all the information are kept in a place with good interactive policy. However it is important to note that proper cross referencing and reputable database should be provided. Information collectors basically can keep their data in a particular or linked database. It is worthy to note that internal and external security threats should be kept in mind. Data encryption as well as different kind of based system may be used for avoiding threat from the outside.
5. **Enforcement:** Enforcement may be treated as the redress. It is important to note that fair information practice is only possible with good, sophisticated and dynamic enforcement system. There are following three types of enforcement systems viz.-
 - i) **Self regulation** (Here information collector or similar body perform the self regulation)
 - ii) **Private remedies** (Here civil causes of action for the individual: those information are misused)
 - iii) **Government enforcement** (It includes civil and criminal penalties by the government bodies or ministry) [18], [21].

6. Issues and FIPPs

There are various concern about the Fair Information Practice Principles and among these few important are included in the collection of data of any human being should be in legal way and by appropriate and authentic means. The personal data should be appropriate, complete and up-to-date in nature. The purpose of the data collection should be specified and personal data should be disclosed. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned it is worthy to note that the security safeguard principles should be modeled and followed as much as possible. Moreover, a general policy regarding the openness about developments, practices as well as policies with respect to personal data may also be undertaken [13], [20].

7. Conclusion

The Fair Information Practice Principles and its importance are important and valuable in different context. The Information development is the root for the development of any kind of Organizations, Institutions and government bodies those are doing well in terms of better information practice. Information Practice is included in the affairs of information leading to collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned, the role of information governance is treated as vital one. Previously only developed countries have focused on better and healthy Information Practice and thus different nations have developed various policies and framework on this. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned it may be called as Personal Data Protection or Simply Data Protection. For the successful information practice we need to follow-up all the steps and procedure as much as possible.

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